

THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN IMPROVING EMPLOYEE QUALIFICATION

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Abstract. *This article will look into the issue of applying technology in the process of improving qualification of employees. The article will provide opinions and suggestions of scholars on training and technology designing which emphasize the role of technology to achieve the development of qualification. The reasons and the importance of technology in this field will be discussed thoroughly.*

Keywords: *adaptation, LMS, labor market, workflow, Coursera, Udemy, and LinkedIn Learning.*

Introduction

In order to maintain their position in the labour market, it is now more crucial than ever to keep employees informed about global advancements. Employees and their qualifications need to be improved and retrained for a number of reasons. Adapting to changes in technology is one of them. Employees must learn new skills as technology advances in order to stay up to date with the newest instruments and procedures.

In addition, there is competition. Businesses that spend money on employee training are better equipped to handle changes in the market and in technology. Increasing efficiency and production is another justification for it. Frequent retraining aids in filling skill gaps, which boosts output and enhances performance. Workflows are more efficient when well-trained staff members are able to exploit new technology and approaches more skillfully.

Another reason why we need retraining or improving employees and their qualification is career development. Providing training opportunities demonstrates that an organization values its employees' growth, leading to higher job satisfaction and morale. Employees are more likely to stay with a company that invests in their professional development, reducing turnover costs.

Ongoing education guarantees adherence to the special training needs that many companies have in order to comply with regulations. Maintaining high standards of quality in goods and services is facilitated by ongoing training. A workforce with proper training is better able to think critically and come up with new ideas, which propels the company forward. Training promotes teamwork and information exchange, which can result in fresh concepts and advancements. Retraining guarantees that workers are ready for new challenges and responsibilities as job roles change. Putting money into staff development helps build a talent pool for the organization's future leadership positions.

Organisations must retrain and improve their workforce if they want to stay competitive, encourage innovation, and improve overall performance. By investing in employee qualifications, businesses foster a healthy work environment that promotes growth and development in addition to having a more skilled workforce.

Keeping up with technical advancements is essential in today's technologically advanced environment, and retraining or training procedures should be modified and enhanced accordingly. Technology has a big and complex function in raising employee qualities.

Platforms like Coursera, Udemy, and LinkedIn Learning offer a wide range of courses that employees can take to enhance their skills. Employees can learn at their own pace and on their own schedule, making it easier to balance work and education.

Engaging online modules that incorporate quizzes, videos, and interactive content to enhance understanding. Tools that allow employees to practice skills in a safe, controlled environment.

There are also mobile learning applications. Mobile apps enable employees to access training materials anytime and anywhere, making learning more convenient. Short, focused learning segments that fit easily into a busy workday. Learning Management Systems (LMS) are its another significance. LMS platforms allow organizations to monitor employee progress and tailor training programs to individual needs. Centralized repositories for training materials, making it easier to share resources across the organization.

Technology enables immediate feedback on performance, helping employees identify areas for improvement. Online assessments and quizzes evaluate skills and knowledge retention.

More recent one is developing of Artificial Intelligence and Personalization. AI can analyze an employee's skills and recommend personalized learning paths to address gaps. Systems adjust the difficulty and type of content based on the learner's progress. Technology plays a crucial role in enhancing employee qualifications by providing flexible, accessible, and personalized learning opportunities. It not only improves skill acquisition but also fosters a culture of continuous learning within organizations.

Literature review

Scholar Dr. Ruth Colvin Clark, a specialist of Instructional Design and E-Learning, emphasizes the importance of applying research-based instructional design principles when creating online training materials. She suggests that incorporating multimedia elements can enhance learning retention. Organizations should develop engaging, interactive e-learning modules that cater to different learning styles.

Moreover, Dr. Tony Bates, who is in Distance Education and E-Learning, argues that technology should be aligned with pedagogical strategies to effectively meet learning objectives. Organizations should take a strategic approach to technology integration, ensuring that training programs are designed with clear educational goals in mind.

Dr. Jay Cross is a specialist of Informal Learning and Knowledge Management. Dr. Cross emphasizes that informal learning, supported by technology, can be more impactful than formal training. Organizations should leverage social media and collaboration tools to facilitate knowledge sharing and peer learning among employees.

Another scholar who emphasizes the importance of technology in retraining is Dr. Harold Jarche. He devotes his works to knowledge management and learning in the digital age. Dr. Jarche stresses the importance of personal knowledge management (PKM) in employee development, particularly in the digital era. Companies should provide tools and resources that support PKM practices, allowing employees to manage their own learning.

Dr. Jennings discusses the 70:20:10 model, which suggests that 70% of learning occurs through experience, 20% through social interactions, and only 10% through formal training.

Organizations should create environments that promote experiential learning and social collaboration while using technology to facilitate these processes. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Charles Jennings model

In conclusion, improving and retraining employees is crucial for organizations to remain competitive, foster innovation, and enhance overall performance. By investing in employee qualifications, companies not only benefit from a more skilled workforce but also create a positive work environment that encourages growth and development. Increasing employee qualifications across all spheres is necessary to adapt to technological advancements, enhance productivity, and meet industry standards. It fosters innovation, improves employee engagement, and helps retain talent. By investing in continuous training and development, organizations ensure a skilled workforce that can effectively navigate changes and drive success.

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